

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the issues of developing small businesses and private entrepreneurship in the digital economy. Factors such as increasing the efficiency of business entities through the introduction of digital technologies, expanding their access to markets, and improving the quality of interactive services are considered. Also, problems such as the existing infrastructure, the level of digital literacy, information security, and regional differences are identified, and scientific and practical proposals are developed to eliminate them. Based on the results of the research, the need for a comprehensive and phased approach to the digitization of small businesses is substantiated.

Keywords: Digital economy, small business, private entrepreneurship, digital transformation, e-commerce, digital literacy, information security, state support, innovative infrastructure, territorial inequality.

Digital technologies have become an integral part of the modern economy and are becoming the basis for fundamental reforms in all areas. The development of digital infrastructure, especially in the areas of small business and private entrepreneurship, is fundamentally changing the business environment. The Republic of Uzbekistan is pursuing a consistent policy in this direction, and the implementation of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy is creating new opportunities for business entities [1]. This strategy is aimed at forming the foundations of the digital economy, transforming public services into electronic form, and strengthening IT infrastructure.

Small businesses and private entrepreneurship are recognized as an important factor in the country's economic development, serving as a key tool for ensuring employment, diversifying sources of income, and achieving social stability [3]. Digital technologies are becoming an important factor in increasing the efficiency of these sectors, expanding access to markets, and improving the quality of customer service. From this perspective, accelerating technological integration for small businesses in the digital economy is a priority.

Also, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4699 of April 28, 2020, established a comprehensive set of measures for the

development of the digital economy [2]. This resolution is aimed at ensuring the active participation of small business representatives in the areas of e-government, digital financial services, and e-commerce. At the same time, existing problems in the field - human resource capacity, level of digital literacy, and regional disparities - still remain relevant.

Currently, the issue of increasing the flexibility of small businesses in the context of economic and technological transformation is being studied in depth from a scientific and practical perspective. Experts note that the introduction of digital solutions in small businesses serves to increase efficiency and innovative activity [4]. Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of this process and the development of solutions based on an integrated approach to existing problems are urgent tasks today.

In recent years, the development of the digital economy has radically changed the activities of small businesses and private entrepreneurship, and many scientific studies have been carried out in this area. In particular, XX Toirov in his study analyzed the role of the presence of digital infrastructure in expanding the activities of small businesses and increasing their efficiency [5]. According to the author, the rate of creation of new business entities is also significantly faster in regions with a high level of use of digital services.

Also, research conducted by SS Kadirova has highlighted that the level of digital literacy and skills in using digital technologies of small businesses directly affect their competitiveness [6]. This study specifically analyzes the benefits of accessing e-commerce platforms and automating tax reporting.

Another important study was conducted by BT Rajabova, which highlighted the institutional framework for small business support policies in the digital economic environment [7]. The author analyzed the role of state-created coordination systems (for example, the "Single Interactive State Services Portal") in the digitalization of entrepreneurship and their effectiveness based on statistical data. She also highlighted the favorable aspects of state policy in the digitalization of small businesses, such as tax breaks and online access to credit resources.

In his research, MT Khudoyberganov discussed the challenges of digitizing small businesses, including insufficient technical infrastructure, a shortage of qualified IT specialists, and digital disparities between regions [8]. The author assessed the effectiveness of digital reforms across regions by modeling the economic consequences of these problems.

At the international level, organizations such as the World Bank, UNCTAD (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development), and OECD (Economic Co-operation and Development) have developed specific strategies to prepare small businesses for digital transformation, provide them with digital infrastructure, and implement innovative solutions [9]. These documents propose flexible digital strategies for developing countries, in particular, for economies like Uzbekistan .

The above-mentioned scientific research and analysis show that the development of small businesses in the digital economic environment is a pressing and multifaceted issue, requiring not only a technological, but also a social, legal and infrastructural approach. Scientific work reveals not only the existing opportunities in this area , but also the issues that need to be addressed.

The digital economy has become an important factor in modern business activity, opening up wide opportunities for small businesses and private entrepreneurs. The consistent policy pursued in the Republic of Uzbekistan , the expansion of digital infrastructure and the measures envisaged within the framework of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy contribute to the sustainable development of this sector. Research shows that the active introduction of digital technologies by small businesses allows them to increase their operational efficiency, reduce costs, enter new market segments and improve interactive communication with customers.

to be addressed in this area . In particular, low levels of digital literacy, insufficient technical infrastructure in some regions, information security threats , and a shortage of qualified IT personnel prevent small businesses from fully benefiting from digital transformation. The economic infrastructure and regulatory framework also need to be improved to meet the needs of the times.

From this perspective, a comprehensive approach to adapting small businesses and private entrepreneurship to the conditions of the digital economy is important. This approach should include, in addition to the introduction of digital technologies, training personnel, improving the digital form of public services, expanding e-commerce opportunities, and eliminating regional inequalities .

, it is important to strengthen innovation infrastructure, develop technological cooperation based on public-private partnerships, and implement international experiences in order for small businesses to become full-fledged participants in the digital economy. This will not only contribute to economic

growth , but also to the formation of innovative thinking and technological culture in society

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